

DELAMINATION BUCKLING OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH WITH LAMINATED FACES

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ABSTRACT

Consider a sandwich plate with anisotropic composite laminated faces and an ideally-orthotropic honeycomb core. The stiffness property of the laminate is characterized by the way similar to the classical lamination theory. The honeycomb cellular core is considered as a homogeneous orthotropic continuum and the effective moduli which can be related to the geometry and actual material properties of the core are used to represent the honeycomb. Based upon this material characterization, the paper presents elastic buckling analysis of an axially loaded plate with an across-the-width delamination symmetrically located at the interface of the upper face and core. For nondelamination problems, the two-dimensional analysis has been performed and an explicit closed form solution for the buckling load has been derived. For the delaminated composite sandwiches, we consider only the cylindrical bending deformation and a simplified one-dimensional mathematical model is proposed. By applying the one-dimensional formulations, the transverse deflection and bending moment of the postbuckling solutions can be obtained. An explicit closed form solution for the critical buckling load is then derived by considering the stage immediately after the buckling of the delaminated sandwiches.

KEYWORDS: Delamination; Buckling; Core, Honeycomb; Laminate; Sandwich Construction

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich construction has been used in aeronautical applications for more than forty

years. Today, there is a renewed interest in using sandwich structures due to the introduction of new materials such as laminated composites for the faces and honeycombs for the core. However, these new materials also induce some new problems which need to be solved. One of the most frequently encountered problems in composite laminates is interface cracking, sometimes known as delamination. For composite sandwiches, there is an extra interface between the face and core which may be weaker than those within the layered composite faces. The presence of delaminations is of major concern especially in compressively loaded components where delaminations may grow under fatigue loading by out-of-plane distortion.

Although there are some papers dealing with the buckling problem of composite sandwich [1-6], none of them consider delamination except Vizzini et al.[4]. As to the buckling of a delaminated composite, several works have been done, for example, [7-9]. In this paper, we first consider the buckling of a perfect sandwich (without delamination) by a way similar to the classical lamination theory [10]. An explicit closed form solution is obtained for the composite sandwiches, composed of the cross-ply symmetric laminated faces and honeycomb core, with simply supported edges under uniform compression. For the delaminated composite sandwiches, a one-dimensional mathematical model similar to those proposed by Chai et.al. [7] is developed. Based upon this model, a characteristic equation for the critical buckling load of the delaminated composite sandwiches is also obtained in this paper.

2. FACE AND CORE PROPERTIES

The following assumptions are usually made when dealing with sandwich panels, and are adopted here to simplify the theory [11]: (1) The faces are relatively thinner than the depth of the core. (2) The faces carry loads in their own planes only. (3) The core has direct stiffness normal to the faces and shear stiffnesses in planes normal to the faces, but no other stiffnesses. (4) The face-to-core bond ensures that any displacement in the core adjacent to the faces is reproduced exactly in faces, and vice versa. According to these assumptions, the faces take almost all the in-plane loadings and bending moments, while the core undergoes only transverse shear forces. Hence, in the following we consider only in-plane stiffnesses of the faces and transverse shear stiffnesses of the core.

2.1 Face Properties Consider each lamina of a laminated face to be composed of orthotropic materials of which the stress-strain relations in principal material coordinates are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{ij} are the reduced stiffnesses and may be expressed in terms of the engineering constants E_1, E_2, ν_{12} and G_{12} [10]. By classical lamination theory, the stiffness property of the laminate may be characterized by the following relation,

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{x_o} \\ \epsilon_{y_o} \\ \gamma_{xy_o} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij} are called the extensional stiffnesses, coupling stiffnesses and bending stiffnesses, which are related to the location and the transformed reduced stiffnesses (\bar{Q}_{ij}) of each lamina [10]; N_x, N_y, N_{xy} are the in-plane stress resultants; M_x, M_y, M_{xy} are the bending and twisting moments; $\epsilon_{x_o}, \epsilon_{y_o}, \gamma_{xy_o}$ are the middle surface strains; $\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}$ are the middle surface curvatures. For sandwich plates considering finite deformation, we have [12]

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{x_o} &= \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x} \right)^2, \\ \epsilon_{y_o} &= \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w_o}{\partial y} \right)^2, \\ \gamma_{xy_o} &= \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial y}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_x &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\gamma_{xz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x} \right), \\ \kappa_y &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\gamma_{yz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial y} \right), \\ \kappa_{xy} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\gamma_{xz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\gamma_{yz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial y} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where (x, y, z) is the coordinate in the unstrained configuration with the origin located on the center of the middle plane of the core; u_o, v_o, w_o are the displacements of the plane $z = 0$ in the x, y, z directions; γ_{xz} and γ_{yz} are the transverse shear strains in the x - z and y - z planes.

2.2 Core Properties By treating honeycomb as a homogeneous orthotropic continuum, Penzien and Didriksson [13] suggested a formula to predict the effective shear moduli of the honeycomb, which is

$$\frac{G_e}{G} = \frac{t \sin \theta (b + a \cos \theta)}{a(a+b) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \phi + (b + a \cos \theta)^2 \sin^2 \phi} \quad (5)$$

where a, b, t, θ are geometric properties of the honeycomb (Figure 1), and ϕ is the angle between the shear resultant force and the longitudinal x - axis. Note that in this formula

the effect of the prevention of warpage has been ignored. Other predictions can also be found in [3]. The effective transverse shear moduli G_{xz} and G_{yz} can therefore be obtained from eqn.(5) by letting $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$. The transverse shear forces Q_x, Q_y contributed by the core are then calculated as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{Bmatrix} = c \begin{Bmatrix} G_{xz} \gamma_{xz} \\ G_{yz} \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

where c is the thickness of the core.

3. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The equilibrium equations for the buckled plate expressed by the resultant forces are [14]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial Q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y}{\partial y} + N_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} + N_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} &= Q_x, \\ \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} &= Q_y. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By using (2)-(4) and (6), the five equilibrium equations for the buckled sandwich plate given in (7) can be written in terms of five unknowns $u_o, v_o, w_o, \gamma_{xz}$ and γ_{yz} . For cross-ply symmetric laminate faces, $A_{16} = A_{26} = D_{16} = D_{26} = 0, B_{ij} = 0, i, j = 1, 2, 6$. If one considers small deflection, the nonlinear terms in eqn.(3) can be neglected. Under these special considerations, the in-plane and plate bending problems are uncoupled and can be treated individually. For plate bending problems, only the last three equations of (7) should be considered. By substituting (2)-(4) and (6) into (7)_{3,4,5} with the above considerations, we obtain the governing equations as

$$\begin{aligned} (N_x \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + N_y \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y}) w_o + cG_{xz} \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x} + cG_{yz} \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial y} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [D_{11} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + (D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}] w_o - \\ [D_{11} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + D_{66} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} - cG_{xz}] \gamma_{xz} - (D_{12} + D_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x \partial y} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [D_{22} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + (D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}] w_o - \\ [D_{22} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + D_{66} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - cG_{yz}] \gamma_{yz} - (D_{12} + D_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x \partial y} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

For one dimensional problems, the governing equation for buckled sandwich beam can also be reduced from (2)-(7) as [12]

$$\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + \lambda^2 w = c_1 x + c_2, \quad (9a)$$

where

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{P}{\left(D_{11} - \frac{B_{11}^2}{A_{11}}\right) \left(1 - \frac{P}{S}\right)}, \quad (9b)$$

$$S = cG_{xz}. \quad (9c)$$

and c_1, c_2 are integration constants which will be determined by the boundary conditions.

4. BUCKLING OF A PERFECT SANDWICH

For a sandwich with cross-ply symmetric laminate faces under small deflections, the governing equation of the plate has been given in (8). Consider the sandwich with simply supported edges subjected to uniform compression in x -direction, the boundary conditions can be described as

$$\begin{aligned} w_o = 0, \quad M_y = 0, \quad \gamma_{xz} = 0, \quad y = 0, \quad b, \\ w_o = 0, \quad M_x = 0, \quad \gamma_{yz} = 0, \quad x = 0, \quad a. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Here an edge stiffener is considered to prevent shear strain. If no forces parallel to the edges of the plate are applied to prevent shear strain, $\gamma_{xz} = 0$ and $\gamma_{yz} = 0$ should be replaced by $M_{xy} = 0$. By eqns.(2)_{4,5}, and $D_{16} = D_{26} = 0$, $B_{ij} = 0$, $i, j = 1, 2, 6$, $M_y = 0$ and $M_x = 0$ can now be replaced by $\frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\gamma_{yz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial y}) = 0$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\gamma_{xz} - \frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x}) = 0$, and the boundary conditions (10) will be satisfied if one assumes

$$\begin{aligned} w_o &= W \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b}, \\ \gamma_{xz} &= \Gamma_x \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b}, \\ \gamma_{yz} &= \Gamma_y \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{b}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Substituting (11) into (8) with $N_x = -P$, $N_y = N_{xy} = 0$, we obtain a system of three simultaneous linear equations in three unknowns W , Γ_x and Γ_y . Nontrivial solutions exist only when the determinant of the coefficients vanishes, which leads to a solution for the buckling load of P . The final simplified result is

$$P_{cr} = \frac{1 + \lambda}{1 + \lambda_x + \lambda_y + \lambda_o} P_o, \quad (12a)$$

where

$$\lambda = \frac{\pi^2 D^*}{c} \left[\frac{1}{G_{yz}} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{G_{xz}} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 \right],$$

$$\lambda_x = \frac{\pi^2}{c G_{xz}} \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 + D_{66} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 \right],$$

$$\lambda_y = \frac{\pi^2}{c G_{yz}} \left[D_{66} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 \right],$$

$$\lambda_o = \frac{D^* P_o m^2 \pi^2}{a^2 c^2 G_{xz} G_{yz}},$$

$$P_o = \frac{\pi^2 a^2}{m^2} \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{mn}{ab} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^4 \right\},$$

$$D^* P_o = \frac{\pi^2 a^2}{m^2} \left\{ D_{11} D_{66} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^4 + [D_{11} D_{22} - D_{12} (D_{12} + 2D_{66})] \left(\frac{mn}{ab} \right)^2 + D_{22} D_{66} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^4 \right\}, \quad (12b)$$

in which only the lowest value of P_{cr} is of any important usually. However it is not clear which value of m and n result in the lowest critical buckling load. All values of n appear in the numerator, so $n = 1$ is the necessary value. But m appears several places and should be determined computationally.

5. BUCKLING OF A DELAMINATED SANDWICH

We now consider a sandwich plate containing an interface crack (delamination) lying between the upper face and core. The plate has a constant width between two lateral edges and is subjected to compressive axial loads P at the clamped ends $x = \pm l$. As shown in Figure 2, the crack extends over an interval $-a \leq x \leq a$ and runs across the whole width of the plate. The delaminated sandwich starts to buckle when the axial load reaches a critical value. If appropriate boundary conditions are maintained along the lateral edges, the plate undergoes cylindrical bending deformation in the postbuckling states. Hence, the one-dimensional governing equation presented in (9) can be employed. To analyze the delaminated sandwich, the entire plate is separated into three regions as shown in Figure 2 and each region is considered as a sandwich beam (region 1 and 2) or laminated beam (region 3). The governing equation (9) is now employed for these three regions. The term containing S vanishes for regions 2 and 3 since $\tau_{xz} = 0$ (or $\gamma_{xz} = 0$) along the crack surfaces provided that the crack remains completely open. By using the symmetry condition with respect to the midpoint, the clamped boundary conditions at the two ends, the continuity of deflection and slope at the crack tip, the equilibrium of forces and moments at the crack tip, and the compatibility of regions 2 and 3, one may obtain the transverse deflection and bending moment of the postbuckling solutions [12].

To determine the buckling load P_{cr} , we consider the stage immediately after the buckling of the delaminated sandwich. At this stage, the deflection amplitude Γ is small and the higher order term of Γ is negligible in comparison with the remaining terms. An explicit closed form solution for the critical buckling load of delaminated sandwich beam has been obtained under this consideration as [12]

$$P_{cr} = (D_2 + D_3 - D_1) \cdot \left\{ \frac{a}{\bar{\lambda}_1 \tan \bar{\lambda}_1 (l - a)} + \frac{ka}{\bar{\lambda}_2 \tan \bar{\lambda}_2 a} + \frac{(1 - k)a}{\bar{\lambda}_3 \tan \bar{\lambda}_3 a} \right\}^{-1}, \quad (13a)$$

where

$$k = \frac{A_3}{A_2 + A_3},$$

$$\bar{\lambda}_1^2 = \frac{P_{cr}}{D_1(1 - \frac{P_{cr}}{S})}, \quad \bar{\lambda}_2^2 = \frac{kP_{cr}}{D_2}, \quad \bar{\lambda}_3^2 = \frac{(1 - k)P_{cr}}{D_3}. \quad (13b)$$

and

$$A_i = \frac{1}{(A_{11})_i}, \quad B_i = \left(\frac{B_{11}}{A_{11}} \right)_i, \quad D_i = \left(D_{11} - \frac{B_{11}^2}{A_{11}} \right)_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (13c)$$

This result is also applicable to the cases of composite laminates (without core) by letting the terms containing S vanish. For a perfect sandwich (without delamination), eqn.(13) reduces to

$$P_{cr} = \frac{D_1 \left(\frac{\pi}{l} \right)^2}{1 + \frac{D_1}{S} \left(\frac{\pi}{l} \right)^2}, \quad (14)$$

which is a well known solution for perfect sandwich beams [15]. Note that eqn.(14) can also be reduced from the two-dimensional solutions presented in section 4, by letting $b \rightarrow \infty$ and $G_{yz} \rightarrow \infty$.

An example of sandwich construction $[\theta_4/90/\text{honeycomb}]_s$ is used to show (Figure 3) the relation between the relative buckling load P_{cr}/P_{cr_0} and delamination length a/l where P_{cr_0} denotes the buckling load of perfect sandwiches. In this example, graphite/epoxy lamina is selected to construct the faces of sandwich while aluminum honeycomb is used to be the core of sandwich. The half length of sandwich beam l is 50 mm. The material properties of graphite/epoxy are [5]

$$E_{11} = 181 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_{22} = 10.3 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{12} = 7.17 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.28$$

where E , G , and ν are the Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. The subscript 1 denotes the fiber direction and the subscript 2 denotes the

transverse direction. The thickness of each lamina t_{ply} is 0.125 mm. The effective transverse shear moduli of aluminum honeycomb selected are $G_{xz} = 0.146$ GPa, $G_{yz} = 0.0904$ GPa, and the thickness of honeycomb core c is 10 mm. As expected, the upper bound solution is approximated by the buckling load of perfect sandwich shown in (14), while the combined axial load of two completely detached beam represents the lower bound. Figure 3 also shows that the buckling loads for some short delaminations are a little higher than P_{cr_0} , which seems unreasonable at a first glance but same phenomenon has been found in experiment [16,17].

6. CONCLUSIONS

By a way similar to the classical lamination theory, a two-dimensional formulation for the composite sandwich plates has been given in this paper. Based upon this formulation, an explicit closed form solution of the critical buckling load for the composite sandwiches with simply supported edges has been derived, where the sandwiches are composed of the cross-ply symmetric laminate faces and honeycomb core. Moreover, a one-dimensional mathematical model for the delaminated composite sandwiches has also been developed in this paper. By applying this model, the transverse deflection and bending moment of the postbuckling solution can be obtained, and a characteristic equation for the critical buckling load is then derived.

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Fig.1 Geometry of Honeycomb Cells

Fig.2 The delaminated composite sandwich

Fig.3 Effect of delamination length on buckling load